

SHORT COMMUNICATIONS

Oxidation of Esters by Chromium^{vi}

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Chromic acid has been a versatile oxidising agent for many classes of compounds.¹ This communication deals with the oxidation of esters by Cr^{vi} in acetic acid (70% v/v) and water (30% v/v) mixtures (Potassium Acetate buffer) at constant pH 3.5 and constant ionic strength 0.2 M. This is the first kinetic report of oxidation of esters by Cr^{vi}. The reactions are clean second order reactions, first order in the substrate and first order with respect to the oxidant. Cyclopentyl, cyclohexyl, bornyl and iso-bornyl acetates have been oxidised and the kinetics of the reactions were followed iodometrically. The products are corresponding ketones identified as their corresponding 2:4-dinitrophenyl hydrazones. It is clear from the differential rate of cyclohexanol and cyclohexyl acetate that these oxidations are not through the alcohols.

70% (v/v) aqueous acetic acid	Temperature 50°
Compound.	10 ³ × k. lit. moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
Cyclohexanol	52.0
Cyclohexyl acetate	2.12

There is no hydrolysis of esters under these conditions. This aspect has been established by Deno and co-workers by Proton Magnetic Spectroscopy.² The rate constants are tabulated below.

70% (v/v) acetic acid-water	Temperature 50°
Compound	10 ³ × k.lit. moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
Cyclopentyl acetate	2.97
Cyclohexyl acetate	2.12
Bornyl acetate	7.63
Iso-bornyl acetate	37.2

The reactivity of the esters cyclopentyl > cyclohexyl is quite in consonance with the ring size. I-strain concept is extended to five and six membered rings which indicates that reactions involving a change in the co-ordination number of 4 to 3 (reactions of SN₁ and free radical type) and from 4 to 5 (reactions of SN₂ and E₂ forming the activated complex) are strongly favoured in the strained rings (viz., five and seven membered rings) but proceed more slowly in the strain free cyclohexane compounds. It is apparent from the above reactivity that the formation transition complex from a molecule of Cr^{vi} and a molecule of the ester should be accompanied by a marked decrease in the number and magnitude of unfavourable constellations with the resultant increase in rate for cyclopentyl acetate.

1. K. B. Wiberg, 'Oxidation in Organic Chemistry', Academic Press, New York, 1965, pp 69-184.
2. N. C. Deno and N. H. Potter, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 3555.

It is well known that in the non-methyl substituted bicyclo (2.2,1)-heptanes (nor-bornanes) the boat equatorial *exo*-alcohol is more stable than the corresponding *endo*-isomer. The stability conditions reverse themselves with the introduction of terminal dimethyl groups at position 7. As a result the boat equatorial *iso*-borneol is less stable than borneol (with boat axial OH group).³

Iso-bornyl acetate and bornyl acetate have same conformations as the corresponding alcohols. The higher reactivity of *iso*-bornyl ester is explained on the basis of rate enhancing relief of steric strain in the transition state. Bornyl acetate oxidises slower because of rate retarding steric strain in the transition state. The reaction proceeds through the formation of a conjugate acid of the ester followed by a rate determining attack on hydrogen by Cr^{vi} on the alcoholic part of the ester leading to alkyl-oxygen fission of the ester (A_{AL}2).

Some of the aliphatic esters have also been subjected to kinetics under the same conditions as the cyclic esters. These are also second order reactions. The products are the corresponding carboxylic acids. Under the conditions of these experiments there is no further oxidation of the carboxylic acids. The rate determining step is the removal of first hydrogen with subsequent rapid steps to yield the carboxylic acid. In the case of *iso*-propyl acetate the product is the ketone. The rate constants are given below :

70% (v/v) aqueous acetic acid—Potassium acetate buffer ; Temperature 50°.

Compound	10 ³ × k.lit. moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
Ethyl acetate	0.64
Benzyl acetate	33.2
<i>n</i> -Propyl acetate	0.55
<i>n</i> -Butyl acetate	0.87
<i>Iso</i> -Propyl acetate	0.51
Ethyl benzoate	0.25
Benzyl benzoate	0.66

An attempt has been made for the first time to study the effect of ternary solvent mixtures in these oxidations. The ternary solvent mixture used was 50% v/v acetic acid + 40% v/v nitrobenzene + 10% v/v water (Potassium acetate buffer). The rate constant obtained exactly falls in between the rate constants obtained for mixtures of 90% v/v acetic acid + 10% v/v water and 50% v/v acetic acid + 50% v/v water.

Substrate	Benzyl Acetate	Temperature 50°
Solvent	10 ³ × k.lit. moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	
90% v/v acetic acid + 10% v/v water		127.8
50% v/v acetic acid + 40% v/v Nitrobenzene + 10% v/v water		38.25
50% v/v acetic acid + 50% v/v water		14.5

The linearity between $\log k$ vs $1/D$ shows that even when ternary solvent mixtures are used, there is no abnormality and the rates can be correlated with change in dielectric constant. Work is in progress with other ternary solvent mixtures to quantitatively predict the effect of dielectric constant on reaction rate. Independent experiments have been done to find whether there is any oxidation of nitrobenzene and there is no oxidation of nitrobenzene under these conditions.

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